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Research Article

STUDYING THE CONTROLLED RELEASE EFFECT OF VARIOUS POLYMER CARRIER ON DRUG RELEASE

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Abstract:

Purpose: The present study was undertaken to understand the polymer-controlled release effect on the drug and evaluation studies of its final product formation. Oral Solid dosage forms prepared using six polymers Eudragit grades RL 100 & L100, HPMC grades 15LV and E15LV, Carbopol and Gum Karaya.

Methodology: Wet granulation method was used to prepare the oral solid dosage forms using Paracetamol as model drug. The prepared oral solid dosage forms

Results & discussion: The physical parameters of post compression evaluation studies and drug release studies were found to be compliant with the I.P standards. The optimized polymer carrier was found to be gum karaya with good controlled release with 88 % at the end 2 hr of drug release studies.

Conclusion: with the obtained results of evaluation it can be concluded that polymer carriers Gum Karaya has shown better post compression parameters and controlled release behavior by dissolution studies fulfilling the current study objective.

Keywords: Polymer Carrier, Paracetamol, Controlled Release.

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INTRODUCTION:

Polymers as carrier's usage has widely known in pharmaceutical and biomedical applications with multifunctionality depending upon the amount of usage and dosage form selection. Each polymer selected has known to be used in various pharmaceutical formulations to fulfill the objective of drug delivery either with controlled or immediate release. A proper selection with suitable dosage form has to be prepared to achieve the desired drug release. In this study polymers eudragit with grades RL 100 & L100 was selected for its wide known properties like controlled release and coating material masking the taste, odour and HPMC also known for its sustained release effect and tablet formulations formulated with it have good durability and stability¹⁻⁵. gum karaya also known for providing controlled release with swelling property available as a natural polymer.

Carbopol 934 used for its sustained release effect by mucoadhesive property⁶⁻¹⁰. All the polymers selected upon availability and study the post formulation of tablet physical property and drug release by entrapping the drug in the polymer matrix^{11,12}. Controlled release property is desired for the preparation of stable Pharmaceutical formulations especially oral where the drug related undesirable effects are avoided by controlling the release of drug slowly in the desired environment¹³. Controlled release obtained in tablet dosage forms available as matrix tablets, swellable tablets, mucoadhesive tablets and controlled release tablets based on the mechanism of release allowed by the polymer¹⁴⁻¹⁶. which eventually reduces the frequency of dosing and avoiding medications that come with the side effects of potent dose treatment regimen. Hence in the current study to study various polymers having the controlled release effect were compared for its drug release with equal amounts forming stable formulations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: The materials and the instruments used with its source given in table no.1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE NO.1 LIST OF MATERIALS USED WITH SOURCE

S.NO	MATERIAL	SOURCE
1	PARACETAMOL	ZEN CHEMICALS
2	EUDRAGIT RL100	FISCHER CHEMIC LIMITED CHENNAI INDIA
3	EUDRAGIT L100	OXFORD LAB FINE CHEMICAL LLP
4	CARBOPOL 934	OXFORD LAB FINE CHEMICAL LLP
5	GUM KARAYA	POWER PACK CHEM
6	HPMC 15LV	SPAN CHEMIE
7	HPMC E 15LV	PIOMA CHEMICAL
8	MAGNESIUM STERATE	OXFORD LAB CENTRE FINE CHEM
9	TALC	VASUNDHARA MICRO MINERAL INFENITE
10	LACTOSE	LACTOSE INDIA LIMT

TABLE NO.2 – LIST OF INSTRUMENTS USED WITH SOURCE

S.NO	NAME OF INSTRUMENTS	SOURCE
1	WEIGHING MACHINE	HOPPER WEIGHING SCALE
2	TRAY DRYER	ACE INDUSTRIES
3	TABLET PUNCHING MAHINE	SED PHARMA
4	DISSOLUTION TEST APPARATUS	LAB INDIA ANALYTICAL INSTRUMENT MUMBAI
5	HARDNESS tester	PFIZER HARDNESS TESTER
6	FRIABILITY TEST APPARATUS	HINDUSTAN APPARATUS(HAMCO)

Preparation of oral solid dosage forms: Accurately weighed all the ingredients given in table. no. and mixed in motor and pestle kneaded well with addition of wetting agent and passed the wet mass through the sieve no. 8 and then dried the granules in tray dryer for 20-30 min and added the lubricant and glidant and triturated in motor and pestle and finally passed through sieve no.20 and measured unit dose of each formulation and punched into tablet.

Table NO. 3 working formula of formulations P1-P6

s.no	Ingredients (mg)	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
1.	Drug	100	100	100	100	100	100
2.	Polymer (50mg)	Eudragit RL100	Eudragit L100	Gum karaya	HPMC15LV	HPMCE15LV	CARBOPLO 934
3.	Lactose	250	250	250	250	250	250
4.	Magnesium stearate	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
5.	Talc	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
6.	Microcrystalline cellulose	150	150	150	150	150	150
7.	Total weight	500	500	500	500	500	500

Post compression evaluation parameters: Each formulation were tested for weight variation by measuring the weight of each tablet and mean weight of each formulation were noted. The physical dimensions like diameter and thickness of the tablet of each formulation were measured using Vernier calipers with zero error set and an average dimension and thickness were noted. For the swelling test tablet from each formulation were observed for swelling time placed in petri dish with 6.8 pH phosphate buffer. Friability test was performed by pre-weighing the 20 tablets and after operating at 100 revolutions at 25 RPM weighed for difference of weight loss and determined the value. hardness of all six formulations were measured using PFIZER hardness tester where the breakage of tablet observed by placing diagonally.

Drug release studies: LABINDIA dissolution test apparatus type II was used with conditions temperature 37⁰ C and 25 RPM speed each tablet

placed in the bowl placed with 1N HCL for 1hr initially and buffer changed with 6.8pH phosphate buffer at intervals of 15 min. and determined the drug release by the calibration curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Calibration curve determination of Paracetamol in 6.8 pH Phosphate buffer: 6.8 pH Phosphate buffer prepared according to the standard preparation method given in I.P. accurately weighed 10mg of Paracetamol was dissolved in 10ml of ethanol preparing stock solution and from the stock solution progressive dilutions made with 6.8pH Phosphate buffer to obtain 2,3,4,5,6 ug/ml concentrations separately in standard flasks and measured spectrophotometrically using LABINDIA ANALYTICAL Model 2000 UV-VISIBLE spectrophotometer at 243 nm and plotted the results with concentration on X-axis and absorbance on Y-axis in MS-EXCEL where the regression value and the correlation equation was obtained.

Table NO.4 Standard graph preparation of Paracetamol in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer.

S.NO	CON (ug/ml)	ABS (nm)
1	0	0
2	2	0.423
3	3	0.582
4	4	0.784
5	5	0.931
6	6	0.994

Figure NO. 1 Calibration curve of Paracetamol in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer.

POST COMPRESSION EVALUATION PARAMETERS OF ORAL SOLID DOSAGE FORMS: All the six formulations were evaluated for weight variation test, diameter, thickness, friability and swelling test and all the results shown within the acceptable criteria and uniform physical dimensions given in table no..

TABLE NO.5: Post compression evaluation parameters of formulations (P1-P6).

Formulation	Weight variation (mg)	Diameter (cm)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability	Swelling Test (mins)
F1	495	1.3	0.4	5.2	1.3	2
F2	496	1.3	0.4	7.3	0.99	3.5
F3	499	1.3	0.4	8.0	0.86	6
F4	498	1.3	0.4	5.3	0.83	5
F5	498	1.3	0.4	6.2	0.56	4
F6	495	1.3	0.4	7.2	1.3	7

Drug Release Studies: LABINDIA Dissolution test apparatus type II paddle was used to study the drug release in two different media 1N HCl and 6.8 pH phosphate buffer for 1hr each with 15 min time interval 5 ml sample collected and replenished with equal amount of the same buffer and observed for the drug release in UV-VISIBLE spectrophotometer, the results obtained given in table no. and data presented in figure no.

TABLE NO.6: % Drug release of formulations (P1-P6)

S NO	TIME (hr)	% DRUG RELEASE OF FORMULATION					
		P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
1	0.25	29.98	31.19	33.75	45.62	49.70	24.31
2	0.50	46.11	44.82	42.77	52.30	58.33	44.76
3	0.75	58.17	68.06	49.15	67.15	66.97	59.53
4	1.00	69.54	68.31	55.17	75.91	77.12	62.03
5	1.25	77.34	72.32	63.02	79.32	81.80	68.36
6	1.50	82.67	78.56	79.52	83.87	89.76	79.51
7	1.75	86.32	87.33	84.51	86.24	93.42	87.56
8	2.00	91.33	93.04	88.23	92.65	95.34	93.04

FIGURE NO.2 % Drug release formulations P1-P6

CONCLUSION:

In the current project, we tried to understand the various polymer effect on drug release. Each polymer showed varied characteristics observed in post-compression evaluation parameters & dissolution studies. We hereby conclude by our current study that gum karaya has shown good results in oral solid dosage forms and each polymer showing its unique characteristics can be selected for formulation of various drugs & its dosage form.

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